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Machine Learning Based Approaches for Ultimate Compression Capacity Prediction of Concrete Filled Double Skin Steel Tube Columns

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Abstract

This paper presents the machine learning-based methods that construct the accurate model prediction for the maximum compression capacity responses of concrete filled double skin steel tube (CFDST) columns under uniaxial compression forces. The so-called surrogate-assisted model is generated from the set of training data collected from available experimental results. The dataset is classified into two classes, namely the behaviors of short (section failure) and long (member failure) CFDST columns. Two machine learning, including gaussian process regression (GPR) and extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), methods are encoded in this study. The input data considers geometry (i.e., external and internal diameters/thicknesses of steel tubes, and column length) and material properties (concrete compressive strength, and yield strengths of external and internal steel tubes) of the columns. The output data is the maximum compression capacity of the CFDST columns. The total training datasets comprise of 122 data from the short column tests and 146 data from the long column tests. The surrogate-assisted models determine the accurate uniaxial compression strengths for both short and long CFDST columns, where the good comparisons with relevant standard design specifications are evidenced. The long column responses given by the GPR model are more accurate than those performed by the XGBoost approach, but the short column responses given by the XGBoost approach are more accurate than those performed by the GPR.

Keywords: Concrete filled columns; Double skin steel tubes; Machine learning; GPR; XGBoost.

Introduction

In recent years, the realm of computer science has experienced notable progress, particularly in the domains of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) systems. These intelligent systems can seamlessly integrate with various engineering functionalities, offering structural engineers the ability to predict structural responses based on reliable input data. However, the AI and ML applications in structural engineering remain relatively limited, necessitating further exploration and study.

Concrete filled double steel tube (CFDST) columns depicted in Figure 1 possess numerous advantages owing to their exceptional strength and capacity to absorb substantial energy, making them highly suitable for seismic resistance in the construction of tall buildings, bridges and large structures. Alongside their remarkable load-bearing capabilities, the CFDST columns offer the additional benefits of rapid construction and reduce labor requirements, resulting in cost savings. Ongoing researches focus on the load capacity responses and their

predictive equations that assist engineers to design the CFDST columns accurately and the modification of relevant standard specifications, e.g., EUROCODE 4 and AISC [1, 2].

This study presents the two ML-based, called gaussian process regression (GPR) and extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), methods to construct the surrogate-assisted model that can accurately approximate the maximum uniaxial compression capacities of CFDST columns. Two classes of (namely short and long) column responses are considered. The surrogate-assisted models are trained from the available dataset, including 122 short column tests in one case and 146 long column tests in the other. The accuracy of the generated predictive models are investigated through the comparisons with design standard specifications. The most efficient ML method suiting the CFDST column applications is summarized.

Methodology

Basic principle

The prediction models developed to estimate the compression capacity of CFDST columns are categorized into two distinct models based on the columns' weight-bearing behaviors: one for short columns and another for long columns. The machine learning algorithms employed in this research encompasses GPR and XGBoost. The dataset adopts in training the algorithms included both experimental test data and data generated through the ABAQUS simulation program.

The evaluation of model performance relies on the R^2 coefficient of determination, as defined by the following equation:

$$R^2 = 100 \times \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - y'_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \right), \quad (1)$$

where y_i represents the experimental data, y'_i represents the predicted values, and \bar{y} denotes the mean of the experimental data. The obtained accuracy of the models is subsequently compared with that of established design codes such as AISC and EUROCODE 4. By employing this evaluation metric, the research aims to assess the efficacy of the machine learning models in predicting the compression capacity of CFDST columns and gauge their alignment with industry-standard design practices.

Figure 1. Cross section of CFDST.

AISC specifications

The original AISC specification [2] provides an equation specifically designed for steel reinforced concrete columns. To employ with Concrete Filled Double Steel Tube (CFDST) columns, there are two sets of equations to consider:

Case 1: $P_e < 0.44P_o$

$$(P_u)_{AISC} = 0.8777P_e, \quad (2)$$

Case 2: $P_e \geq 0.44P_o$

$$(P_u)_{AISC} = P_o \left[0.658 \sqrt{\frac{P_o}{P_e}} \right], \quad (3)$$

where P_o and P_e can be calculated from equations (4) and (5), f_{syo} and f_{syi} are the yield strength of the external and internal steel tubes, A_{so} and A_{si} are the section area of the internal and external steel tubes, and f'_c and A_c are the compressive strength of the concrete and section area of the concrete, respectively. K is for long columns using pinned support which is equal to 1 and L is the length of an unbracing column.

The parameter $(EI)_{eff}$ can be calculated from equation (6) where E_{so} and E_{si} are the Elastic Modulus of the external and internal steel tubes and E_{cm} can be calculated from equation (7). K_c is calculated from equation (8) with a maximum value of 0.9. W_c is the weight unit of concrete and has a value in the range 2300-2500 kg/m³.

$$P_o = f_{syo}A_{so} + 0.95f'_cA_c + f_{syi}A_{si}, \quad (4)$$

$$P_e = \frac{\pi^2(EI)_{eff}}{(KL)^2}, \quad (5)$$

$$EI_{eff} = E_{so}I_{so} + K_cE_{cm}I_c + E_{si}I_{si}, \quad (6)$$

$$E_{cm} = w_c^{1.5} 0.043 \sqrt{f'_c}, \quad (7)$$

$$K_c = 0.6 + 2 \left(\frac{A_{so}}{A_c + A_{so}} \right) \leq 0.9. \quad (8)$$

EUROCODE4 specifications

The original EUROCODE4 equation is for Concrete Filled Steel Tubular (CFST), so for CFDST it was modified to add the factor of having an internal steel tube. There are thus 2 cases of equations:

Case 1: $\bar{\lambda} \leq 0.5$

$$(P_u)_{EC4} = n_a f_{syo} A_{so} + f'_c A_c \left[1 + n_c \left(\frac{t_o}{D_o} \right) \left(\frac{f_{syo}}{f'_c} \right) \right] + n_a f_{syi} A_{si}, \quad (9)$$

Case 2: $\bar{\lambda} > 0.5$

$$(P_u)_{EC4} = f_{syo} A_{so} + f'_c A_c + f_{syi} A_{si}, \quad (10)$$

Where n_a and n_c are reduction factor due to slenderness of column, and can be calculated as follows:

$$n_a = 0.25(3 + 2\bar{\lambda}) \leq 1.0, \quad (11)$$

$$n_c = 4.9 - 18.5\bar{\lambda} + 17\bar{\lambda}^2 \geq 0. \quad (12)$$

Next, $\bar{\lambda}$ can be calculated from equation (13), P_{cr} can be calculated from equation (15) and EI_{eff} can be calculated from equation (16) where $K_c = 0.6$.

$$\bar{\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{P_{pl,Rd}}{P_{cr}}}, \tag{13}$$

$$P_{pl,Rd} = f_{syo}A_{so} + 0.85f'_cA_c + f_{syi}A_{si}, \tag{14}$$

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2(EI)_{eff}}{(KL)^2}, \tag{15}$$

$$EI_{eff} = E_{so}I_{so} + K_cE_{cm}I_c + E_{si}I_{si}. \tag{16}$$

Machine learning refers to the capability of a computing system to autonomously learn and analyze the relationships between input and output data by examining training data. Numerous algorithms exist for machine learning, each with its own strengths and weaknesses depending on the nature of the data. In the present study, the primary algorithms employed are GPR (Gaussian Process Regression) and XGboost. Previous research has demonstrated the efficacy of these algorithms in similar references [3,4].

Training data

For separating between short and long columns, the slenderness ratio [5] is used as in equation (17) where L_e is the effective column length, I is area moment of inertia and A is cross section of composite column.

$$\text{Slenderness ratio} = \frac{L_e}{\sqrt{I/A}} \tag{17}$$

Stub columns are those with slenderness ratio of less than 22 [5]. For stub columns, there are 122 data sets from actual tests [9-13,15-17] for training the machine learning algorithms, and the means came out as in Table 1.

Table 1. Training data for short column model.

Input	Maximum	Minimum	Average
External Diameter (mm)	603.40	114.00	212.33
External Thickness (mm)	6.77	0.90	3.97
F_{yo} (MPa)	535.00	220.00	362.65
Inner Diameter (mm)	402.10	33.50	107.06
Inner Thickness (mm)	5.77	0.90	3.06
F_{yi} (MPa)	425.00	220.00	358.86
F_c (MPa)	141.00	18.70	50.78
High (mm)	2502.00	342.00	617.31
Slenderness Ratio	21.66	5.55	2283.79
N_u EXP (kN)	5383.50	540.00	2283.79

Long columns, defined as those with a slenderness ratio exceeding 22 [5], play a significant role in this study. A total of 28 data sets derived from actual tests [9,14,21], along with 132 data sets obtained from ABAQUS simulations, are employed for training purposes. Evaluation criteria are established based on prior investigations [6, 7]. It should be noted that comparing the predictions generated by the simulations with those derived from real-world tests, the achieved R-Square value reaches an impressive 92.47%, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure .. R-Square values from simulations versus from actual tests

The evaluation of concrete’s compressive capacity involves conducting tests using a 150 × 300 mm cylinder mold, following the established ASTM standard. In order to ensure consistency, data obtained from tests conducted with different types of molds are all converted to the 150 × 300 mm cylindrical mold format. This conversion is achieved by multiplying the results by a specific coefficient, as detailed in previous research [6].

Table 2. Training data for long column model.

Input	Maximum	Minimum	Average
External Diameter (mm)	550.00	114.00	216.67
External Thickness (mm)	10.00	1.96	3.42
F _{yo} (MPa)	549.00	259.00	388.60
Inner Diameter (mm)	250.00	45.00	95.99
Inner Thickness (mm)	10.00	1.96	3.16
F _{yi} (MPa)	549.00	298.00	395.49
F _c (MPa)	53.12	24.50	31.79
High (mm)	6500.00	1200.00	2757.98
Slenderness Ratio	95.93	23.67	48.24
N _u EXP (kN)	9882.58	497.19	2003.23

Result and conclusion

The GPR and XGBoost machine learning algorithms are utilized to create predictive models for the compression capacity of Concrete Filled Double Steel Tubes (CFDST). The predictive models specifically designed for stub columns are trained using data from 122 actual tests, yielding impressive results with an R-Square of 94.02% for GPR and 95.53% for XGBoost. In comparison, the R-Squares for the standard codes, AISC and EC4, are considerably lower at 82.97% and 85.90% respectively, demonstrating the superior accuracy of the machine learning models over the standard code.

On the other hand, for long columns, the algorithms are trained using a combination of data from 16 actual tests and 130 simulations conducted with the ABAQUS program. The resulting predictive models achieve an R-Square of 92.12% for GPR and 89.72% for XGBoost. Although these models exhibit slightly lower accuracy compared to the standard

codes (AISC with an R-Square of 93.43% and EC4 with an R-Square of 94.46%), they still provide valuable insights into the compressive capacity of long CFDST columns.

Overall, the machine learning algorithms showcase their potential by outperforming the standard codes in predicting the compression capacity of stub columns. While the accuracy of the predictive models for long columns is slightly lower, they still offer significant improvements over the standard codes, underscoring the value of incorporating machine learning techniques in the design and analysis of CFDST structures.

Table 3. R-square from each predictive model (stub columns).

Predictive Model	R ²	Average (N _u Exp/N _u Predict)
GPR	94.02	0.94
XGBoost	95.53	1.00
AISC	82.97	1.08
EC4	85.90	0.97

Figure 4. R-Square compared between actual test results and calculations based on the standard design code (Stub column).

Figure 5. R-Square compared between actual test results and predictions made by machine learning algorithm (Stub column).

Table 4. R-square from each predictive model (long columns).

Predictive Model	R ²	Average (N _u Exp/N _u Predict)
GPR	92.12	1.00
XGBoost	89.72	1.03
AISC	94.46	1.00
EC4	93.43	0.85

Figure 6. R-Square compared between actual test results and calculations based on the standard design code (long column).

Figure 7. R-Square compared between actual test results and predictions made by machine learning algorithm (long column).

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